

EARLY PREDICTION OF CRACK DEVELOPMENT USING DIGITAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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ABSTRACT

Digital image correlation (DIC) was used in to explore the heterogeneous surface strain profile developed on the longitudinal ply of a glass fibre epoxy cross-ply laminate loaded in tension. This was done in the attempt to identify key developments and characteristics, within the strain field produced by specimens of 2 mm and 4 mm thickness, which indicate the onset of cracking within the transverse ply. These features were then used to assess if accurate predictions regarding the occurrence and location of fracture can be made before crack propagation.

Analysis of the surface strain profiles, recorded at intervals of progressive loading, revealed characteristic developments local strain maxima for cracks that form at lower than average crack onset load and local strain minima for those that propagate at higher than average onset. It was further shown that strain profiles often transition from relatively plateau gradients into points of inflection with distinct kinks in the strain profile, enabling the identification of cracks to within ± 0.224 mm of their actual location. These progressively became more defined and was most apparent at loads just prior to the onset of cracking, after which the profile maintains fairly consistent growth at subsequent loads. It was further observed that these changes are noticeable at an average of 3.9 kN prior to cracking and for those formed at higher loads, warning intervals averaging 11.5 kN were possible.

It was expected that areas of stress concentration observed on the surface would superimpose the area of the crack. Instead, it appears to have been displaced across the strain profile, often being bounded by two or more subsequent cracks. This was more noticeable in the thicker 4 mm specimen and it was suspected that the reason for this lies within the difference of Poisson's ratio between the transverse and longitudinal plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

A fundamental aspect of composite materials research is understanding how they fail. The basic principles of this are well understood and can be found in any good composites text book, e.g. [1]. However, three rounds of the World Wide Failure Exercise have shown how difficult it can be to model the failure of composite materials e.g. [2-4]. Hence, physical experiments remain at the heart of determining the properties of composite materials.

The nature of composite materials means that it can be difficult to assess damage mechanisms directly because of the combination of fibre and resin opacity. Researchers often have to resort to indirect methods such as X-ray computed tomography (X-ray CT) in order to 'see' the damage that has occurred. Whilst it is feasible to examine a specimen under load in a CT chamber, this is not an entirely trivial undertaking, and there are certain limitations in the size of the specimen that can be examined.

An alternative route, when thinking about the fundamental issues of the effects of damage on composites, is to attempt to marry the optical properties of the resin and glass fibres of a simple system. When this is achieved, the resultant laminate is transparent and enables, for example measurements of crack spacing to be made directly. This formed the basis of some of the seminal work on the damage and performance of composites [5-8].

The current work revisits the experiments of the late 1970s. Whilst there is little to add to the fundamental theories underlying this work and the predictions that can be made based on this, it is a useful starting point when considering methodologies for determining the viability and accuracy of non-destructive evaluation techniques.

Digital image correlation [9], commonly abbreviated to DIC, is a form of non-contacting extensometry. It is particularly useful in situations where there are heterogeneous strain fields, such as in a component of complex design, or where the effects of defects and degradation are to be observed [10-12]. The current work employs DIC as a means to investigate the formation of cracks within [0/90]_s cross-ply composites. The key aims of the investigation are to consider:

- the ability to use this technology to accurately predict the onset and growth of transverse cracking, with particular emphasis on how early the predictions can be made.
- the effects that internal damage has upon the strain field at the surface of composite materials.
- identify key occurrences or features within the surface strain field that indicates signs of crack formation.
- the effects of altering subset and step sizes when using DIC and the consequences that this will have on the gathered results compared to computing time.

The paper is structured as follows. Having completed a short introduction to the context of the paper, the experimental conditions are detailed, which consider the manufacture of [0/90]_s glass fibre reinforced polymer composites, the arrangements for the tensile testing of coupons, and the DIC equipment used. There follow results relating to the assessment of the crack density and a comparison with the literature, the assessment the DIC outputs; discussion around the interrogation of the data and the effectiveness of the technique in this context are presented. The paper closes with key findings and some thoughts on the direction for further work in this area.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two cross-ply laminates were produced using a frame-wound, wet layup route, as described in e.g. [13]. One was 2 mm thick and the other 4 mm; in both cases the layup was [0/90]_s. Strips of material 20 mm and 300 mm long were cut from the panel such that the 90° fibres are internal. The specimens were placed in an Instron 5982 electromechanical test frame, with a 100 kN load cell, and gripped using wedge-action grips suitable for tensile testing.

The use of spray paint has traditionally been considered as one of the best ways to produce a speckle pattern, suitable for a range of materials and settings. More recently, this technique has fallen out of favour because it can result in aliasing and variations in speckle density between components [14-16]. Even with a single operator, using spray paint for bulk speckling can result in visible variations in image greyscale intensity values between coupons. Therefore, even if the user applies the same test parameters for component lighting, contrast between the speckles and base layer will likely vary between components and test coupons [14, 15, 17, 18].

A speckle pattern was produced using Correlated Solutions' speckle generator software. It was optimized for the field of view/area of interest and the camera set up, including focal length, aperture, and chip pixel density using an in-house tool. The optimized pattern was then printed onto self-adhesive transfer paper, manufactured by Sunnyscopa, using a Samsung MultiXpress X7400GX laser printer with a rating of 1,200 x 1,200 dots per square inch (~470 x 470 per square cm), following a method developed in-house [19].

The experiment was controlled and data were collected via Bluehill 3, Instron's proprietary control software. DIC images were captured using a single, dual-camera system using two 9 MPx Manta G-917B cameras (with CCD chops). The cameras were controlled via a Correlated Solutions master/slave controller connected to a VIC-3D control system. A Hedler Profilux LED light source was then placed to one side of each camera, at an angle to the specimen. This was to prevent light directly reflecting from the specimen and onto the camera chip, which may cause oversaturation in the captured images leading to loss of data. VIC Snap, the programme that provides a live feed of the two cameras, was then opened and then inspected to ensure that the specimen was visible in the image frame. Due to the test samples being transparent, a white background was required to provide sufficient levels of contrast for the cameras to recognise the speckle pattern. If shadows formed by the specimen fall onto the area of interest as shown in VIC Snap, the position of the light needs to be adjusted as they may give rise to erroneous data. Also, if a white background would be intrusive to the nature of the experiment, or is not feasible, then an alternative solution is to spray paint the surface of the specimen white prior to the transfer of the speckle. Figure 1 shows the experimental set up.

Figure 1 The experimental setup featuring the use of two light sources incident at an angle to the specimen contrasted against a white background.

Images were initially captured at a rate of one image every six seconds over an area of interest of 130 mm x 20 mm, i.e. the entire speckled region, using LINOS MeVis-C 35mm lenses. In practice, this capture rate was too slow to provide sufficient detail throughout the duration of this test, and so it was increased to one image every three seconds. A further refinement, in order to capture data after the first crack has started to form within the specimen, the image capture rate before the onset of initial cracking was maintained at one image every three seconds but after the appearance of the first crack, the capture rate was increased to one image every second and then resumed. Furthermore, the use of available pixels to capture data was suboptimal since the current image is largely occupied by the white background. Therefore, it was decided that the image should be magnified to make better use of the cameras available, with the compromise of not obtaining data along the full length of the specimen. To do this, the 35 mm lenses were replaced by two Rodagon 80 mm lenses attached to 55 mm extension tubes and LINOS focusing rings. This optical setup was used for two more 2 mm and 4 mm specimens.

Images were captured with Vic-Snap and synchronized with the load, and with optical images captured with a Canon EOS 550D digital camera. The DIC aspects of the experiment were carried out with reference to ‘*A Good Practices Guide for Digital Image Correlation*’ [15]. Analysis of the data was carried out using VIC 3D, and a comparison between the default settings of a subset of 29 pixels and a step size of 11 was carried out with revised settings of a 39 pixel subset and a step size of 12.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Determining Crack Density

Crack density was calculated by counting only cracks that span the entire width of the specimen. After tensile testing, the sample was split into four sections over a gauge length of 130 mm to allow an average crack count to be obtained. A similar method was then used to find the average crack spacing in order to gain confidence and draw a comparison between the results obtained and theoretical crack spacings calculated according to the method described in the literature [5-8], and which are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – A comparison of theoretical crack growth and experimental results for (a) 2 mm specimens and (b) 4 mm specimens. In each case, specimen 1 is represented by \blacklozenge and specimen 2 is shown as \bullet . Standard error is represented by error bars

3.2 Full field strain analysis

Full field strain analysis was carried out using digital image correlation (DIC). Firstly, full length tests were run with three each of the 2 mm and 4 mm specimens. A further test at a magnification of 2.36x was conducted for both thicknesses. The 2.36 magnification gave an area of interest of 55 mm x 20 mm compared to the full length area of interest of 130 mm x 20 mm; more of the available pixels were used, leading to a greater resolution, as summarised in Table 1, and illustrated in Figure 3.

Table 1 : Resolution of the images used for DIC testing in relation to the area of interest being observed. Pixel data was extracted from VIC 3D.

	Trial	Pixels Y	Pixels X	Total Pixels	Pixels Occupied (%)	Gauge Width (mm)	Resolution (DPI)
4 mm	Full	2,280	300	684,000	7.60	18.5	412
	Close	2,630	890	2,340,000	26.0	19.5	1160
2 mm	Full	2,210	294	650,000	7.22	18.5	404
	Close	2,620	870	2,280,000	25.3	19.5	1130

Figure 3 Examples of images used for DIC testing (a) full length specimen area of interest is 130 mm x 20 mm and (b) magnified image area of interest is 55 mm x 20 mm.

Initial review of the captured footage on VIC 3D for both the 2 mm and 4 mm specimens revealed that the surface strain field propagated from right to left as load was increased during the full-length experiments. This effect caused the cracks themselves to follow suit and grow in the same direction, although this trend was not observed at every instance. As might be expected, cracks tended to originate from areas of porosity, due to stress concentration, and continued to travel across the specimen to the other end. It was later discovered that there was a slight imbalance in the gripping of the specimen, causing preferential loading of the specimen to one side rather than in perfect alignment with the loading axis. This was corrected for the testing at greater magnification.

Further analysis into the captured footage revealed that, contrary to initial predictions, the strain transferred to the surface ply following transverse cracking is not guaranteed to be concentrated over the immediate area of the crack. Although direct correlation was seen in multiple instances, in the majority of cases peak strains were recorded in between cracks, in the surrounding area. It was also observed that some consecutive cracks acted as “envelopes” for stress concentration. Both of these cases can be seen in Figure 4. The occurrence of crack formation can be predicted to a certain extent as areas of high strain can be identified. The stress contours display signs of growth as load increases and eventually coalesces as the crack forms. However, there was difficulty in identifying the exact position where cracks occur, as demonstrated by the 4 mm test: cracks do not necessarily form in regions where the highest local surface strain occurs and could instead form an envelope with subsequent cracks of maximum strains. A reason for this occurrence could lie within the thickness of the material used as the 1 mm thick longitudinal ply may have inhibited transfer of strain from the transverse ply as a result of stress relief due to cracking.

The results gathered from the 2 mm and 4 mm full-length specimens were analysed and compared to their magnified counterparts. The strain field over an arbitrary length was recorded live as the specimens were continuously loaded. Data was gathered from these trials by manually placing 100 extraction points over the gauge length and half-way across the gauge width using VIC 3D. After gathering results for the 4 mm specimen full-length trial and comparing it to that obtained for the magnified test, it was apparent that the decrease in resolution has caused some strain data to be lost. There were instances where maximum strain variance reached values of 0.76%. As a result of this, it was decided that analysis should focus on the magnified results. Again, 100 data points placed at the centre of the area of interest, this time spanning a distance covering five fully formed cracks. This was done for the same images gathered for the previous magnified 4 mm and 2 mm tests at the same magnitudes of loading and are presented in Figures 6 -8.

3.3 Discussion

Analysis of the surface strain profile formed over the longitudinal plies revealed characteristic changes across instances of applied loads from 2.5 kN-25 kN. It was identified that multiple instances of the development of strain minima were associated with cracks formed at above average crack onset loading, while strain maxima were found to be linked with cracks formed at below average onset loads. Progressive formation of inflection points and kinks to within ± 0.224 mm of the actual location of cracking in successive profiles were also observed, with the most noticeable changes occurring within profiles plotted just before the crack onset. After which, profiles maintain these changes with each consecutive load case following fracture.

Identification of these characteristics can be found on average as early as 11.5 kN prior to the onset of transverse cracking, but this was often the case for only those formed at higher than average onset loading. Those that initiate below this threshold can usually be detected as early as 3.90 kN prior to damage but this is somewhat subjective to the interpreter’s ability to detect these changes within the strain profile and the interval of the load cases used.

Contrary to the initial prediction of the formation of strain concentrations above the immediate area of transverse ply cracking, it was found that instances of peak strain have been translated across the surface of the longitudinal ply being analysed. It was suspected that the cause of this phenomenon was due to the difference in Poisson’s ratio between the transverse and longitudinal plies. It further appeared to have a greater effect on thicker laminates, leading to the formation of strain “envelopes”, instances where distinctive peak strain was bound between the two neighbouring cracks.

Retesting of the specimens after transverse fracture revealed similar levels of strain recorded with tests prior to damage, with a range of 0-1.8% observed for the 2 mm specimens and 0-2.0% for the 4 mm specimens. Areas of strain concentration appeared to superimpose the transverse cracks, which indicated that the influence of contrasting Poisson's ratio between the piles has little to no effect on the displacement of the surface strain field following the onset of damage.

Finally, the effect of increasing the subset and step sizes from 29 pixels and 7 pixels respectively to the suggested values of 39 pixels and 11 pixels in VIC 3D produced a loss of finer detail of the strain profiles. Many small scale distinguishing variations were found to have been masked by the dominant large scale spikes and drops in strain, while only reducing consumption of computational resources by a marginal amount.

Figure 4: Examples of recorded surface strain fields with increasing load: (a) the magnified 2 mm test, shows the initial development of localised strain concentration contours around the area of eventual crack formation. These isolated developments then show signs of coalescing with characteristic bunching of iso-lines, leading to a small area of stress concentration at the onset of cracking in the final image. Series (b), the magnified 4 mm test, shows similar behaviour as load was increased. However, the localised strain concentrations coalescing did not signify the beginnings of crack formation in the immediate area. Instead the strain continued to grow away from the initial crack until the formation of another crack, effectively closing off the large area of stress concentration forming a containment of stress between subsequent cracks.

Figure 5 Strain field profile for magnified 2 mm trial. Dash-dot lines represents the location of cracks in the transverse ply at the end of the test. Successive curves represents data captured for (a) at 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4) and 15 kN (5) and (b) 6-8.5 kN loading in intervals of 0.5 kN

Figure 6 Strain field profile for the full-length 4 mm trial (a) and magnified 4 mm trial (b). Dash-dot lines indicate the location of cracks in the transverse ply at the end of the test. Successive curves represents data captured at 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4), 15 kN (5), 20 kN (6) and 25 kN (7)

Figure 7 Strain field profile for magnified 2 mm trial. Dash-dot lines represents the location of cracks in the transverse ply. Each successive curve (a) represents data captured at 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4) and 15 kN (5). Each successive curve (b) represents 6-8.5 kN loading in intervals of 0.5 kN with instances of the most characteristic changes in the strain profile at loads just prior to fracture highlighted in red.

(a)

(b)

Figure 8 Strain field profile for magnified area of interest encompassing five cracks (a) 2 mm and (b) 4mm Dash-dot lines represents the location of cracks in the transverse ply. Successive curves represents data captured at (a) 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4) and 15 kN (5) and (b) 2.5 kN (1), 5 kN (2), 7.5 kN (3), 10 kN (4), 15 kN (5), 20 kN (6) and 25 kN (7)

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

An investigation into the feasibility of using digital image correlation (DIC) as a means to predict the onset of cracking was carried out, focussing on transverse cracking in [0/90]_s GFRP laminates. Specimens of thickness of 2 mm and 4 mm were tested and the crack density produced from testing the samples was compared with predictions made using a methodology from the literature. The current work employs DIC as a means to investigate the formation of cracks within [0/90]_s cross-ply composites. Four key aims of the investigation were outlined in the Introduction. These have been addressed throughout the paper and the key findings are that:

- digital image correlation has a great deal to offer in terms of determining full field strain analysis, and in terms of assessing the impact of surface breaking features arising from design and degradation. However, the ability to use this technology to accurately predict the onset and growth of transverse cracking within the internal volume of the sample is relatively limited at the current time. Early predictions can be made to some extent, but further work is required to develop this methodology further.
- the effects that internal damage has upon the strain field at the surface of composite materials has been shown to be more complicated than might be supposed from localised or averaged strain measurements, and the interaction of multiple cracks can be difficult to interpret.
- identification of features within the surface strain field that indicates signs of crack formation is possible, although not in a consistent manner. There is some work to be done in terms of understanding the transfer of strain from the interior to the exterior, particularly in terms of how localised strain contributions contribute to the macro properties.
- the effects of altering subset and step sizes on the resolution of the data were considered. In the current case, increasing the subset size was appropriate although it did lead to some loss of resolution. This came about because the speckle had been optimised for a particular set of conditions, and these were changed during testing. Optimising the speckle pattern for the revised area of interest was not possible at this time, but does point to an area for further work.

A number of areas for further work are suggested from the outcomes of this study. For example, a similar investigation into the surface strain field of a [90/0]_s laminate could be carried out to see the direct development of the surface strain profile within the transverse ply without the issues arising from transition of strain through the longitudinal plies. Future efforts can also be directed towards finding the optimal load instances for strain profiles to be drawn from in order to identify the earliest point at which cracks can be revealed to initiate. The option to use micro-DIC to achieve even greater resolution around crack development could also be explored to reveal finer details of the surface strain field surrounding just one instance of transverse fracture. This can be taken further, to the stage of engineering the specimen to produce a single crack and to study this in more detail. Furthermore, since the quality of the surface finish on the test specimens was observed to be of high importance, future experiments should aim to manufacture specimens to a higher quality to minimise the contamination of surface stress concentrations imposed by indentations or surface porosity.

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